

DEVELOPMENT OF NOVEL SILK FIBROIN-MAGNETITE BIOCOMPOSITES FOR TISSUE ENGINEERING

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this paper is to develop a novel magnetic biocomposite scaffold made of *Bombyx mori* silk fibroin and magnetite nanoparticles for wounds healing in terms of: synthesis, physico-chemical and morphological characterization and *in vitro* biological behaviour assessment. The biocomposites were prepared from silk fibroin solutions and magnetite with various concentrations by solvent casting technique. Composites were investigated by FTIR-ATR spectroscopy and XRD measurements. Morphological investigation including internal structure was employed by SEM and TEM/HRTEM analyses. Biological assay was performed on human adipose derived stem cells isolated from subcutaneous adipose tissue. Results suggested that all the tested magnetic biocomposites display a good biocompatibility *in vitro* on hASCs and could be promising candidates for further wound dressing testing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Silk fibroin is a natural fibrous protein produced by domesticated silkworm *Bombyx mori*, spiders or insects such as *Nephila clavipes* [1-5]. Silks are high molecular weight block copolymers consisting of a heavy (~370 kDa) and a light (~26 kDa) chain with varying amphiphilicity linked by a single disulfide bond [6-9]. These natural silkworm proteins have a highly repetitive amino acid sequence mainly composed of glycine (43%), alanine (31%), and serine (12%) residues [8-12]. The particular sequence of these amino acids with small side chains leads to the formation of hydrophobic domains, thus allowing the formation of thick packs of hydrogen bonded anti-parallel β -sheets [3, 6-9]. Aqueous processing conditions, biocompatibility, good water vapour and oxygen permeability and biodegradability of silk fibroin, along with facile chemical modifications, are attractive features for its use as biomaterial. *Bombyx mori* mulberry silkworms are of the most economic importance, because it is possible to rear them in captivity. The fact that there is a readily available source of silkworm silk has facilitated an understanding of its structure and function.

Biomaterial design is an important element of tissue engineering, incorporating physical, chemical and biological cues to guide cells into functional tissues. Many biomaterials need to degrade at a rate commensurate with new tissue formation to allow cells to deposit new extracellular matrix (ECM) and regenerate functional tissue. In addition, biomaterials may need to include provisions for mechanical support appropriate to the level of functional tissue development.

Therefore, silks have been investigated as biomaterials due to the successful use of silk fibers from *Bombyx mori* as suture material for centuries [1, 12-14]. Its uses rely on the excellent mechanical properties in fibre state, on the possibilities of chemically modifying and processing the protein, lack of toxicity, lack of immune reactions, permeability to water vapours and oxygen [10-14]. The medical applications of natural silk fibroin, regenerated by dissolution and precipitation or chemically modified fibroin refer to the obtaining of suture fibres, materials for wound dressing, obtaining of hydrogels based on fibroin for immobilization or controlled release of active principles, tissue reconstruction and cell culture etc.

Silk scaffolds have been thoroughly studied for potential biotechnological and biomedical applications. To improve the properties of scaffolds, silk fibroin has been blended with various other polymers, which includes synthetic polymers such as polyvinyl alcohol as well as natural macromolecules like gelatin, collagen, elastin, etc [15-19]. In a previous work [14] we have reported the synthesis and complex characterization of silk fibroin/polyacrylamide hydrogels for tissue engineering applications. The use of silk fibroin as a scaffold for tissue engineering is a challenge for scientists all over the world.

Magnetite (Fe_3O_4) is a particular magnetic material and receiving special effort due to its potential applications in high-density data storage, biomaterial applications, catalysis, magnetic resonance imaging, Li-ion batteries, sensors, pigments and others [20-23]. With the rapid development of nanotechnology, magnetic nanoparticles are now being studied all over the world. In recent years, magnetic nanoparticles, especially magnetite has been used to develop a wide range of biomedical and bioengineering applications such as: magnetic resonance imaging, contrast agents, biosensors, cancer hyperthermia and targeted drug delivery [20-23]. Most of the envisaged applications are based on the unique magnetic properties of these nanoparticles, namely, their capacity to display high magnetization in the presence of an external magnetic field and insignificant residual magnetism in its absence. Nanosized magnetic carriers provide good performance due to their higher specific surface area and lower internal diffusion resistance. Based on a recent report, the presence of iron oxide in hydroxyapatite can improve the radiopacity and osteoblast proliferation [22]. Fe_3O_4 doped HA exhibits enhanced solubility in physiological solutions compared with HA [23]. Consequently, magnetite nanoparticles loaded polymeric biomaterials are promising tools for scaffold mediated construction of three-dimensional engineered tissues composed of magnetic controlled orientation of cells and ECM.

The goal of this paper is to develop of a novel magnetic biocomposite scaffold made of *Bombyx mori* silk fibroin and magnetite nanoparticles for wounds healing in terms of: synthesis, physico-chemical and morphological characterization and *in vitro* biological behaviour assessment.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. MATERIALS

Cocoons of *Bombyx mori* silkworm silk were kindly supplied by Marilena Constantinescu, Commercial Society SERICAROM SA (Bucharest, Romania). Lithium bromide (LiBr), sodium bicarbonate and sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) were provided by Alfa Aesar GmbH&Co KG, Germany and dialysis tubing cellulose membrane from Sigma. All other chemicals (of analytical grade) were supplied from Sigma Aldrich and are used as received. Magnetic nanoparticles of Fe_3O_4 were obtained directly by co-precipitation using ammonia solution.

2.2. METHODS

Obtaining of silk fibroin solution

Bombyx mori silkworm cocoons were boiled for 40 min in an aqueous solution of 0.5 % (w/v) NaHCO_3 and SDS and then rinsed thoroughly with distilled water to extract the sericin protein. This operation was repeated three times to get the pure silk fibroin. The degummed silk fibroin was dried at 45 °C and atmospheric pressure. The extracted silk fibroin was then dissolved in a 9.3 M LiBr solution at 65 °C for 12 h, yielding a 8 % (w/v) solution. This solution was dialyzed in distilled water using a dialysis tubing cellulose membrane (molecular weight cutoff, MWCO, 12.4 kDa) for 4 days (frequent water changes). The final concentration of the silk fibroin aqueous solution was 3 wt. %, which was determined by weighing the remaining solid after drying.

Preparation of silk-fibroin magnetite biocomposites (SF-MAG)

For the SF-MAG biocomposite preparation, the clear silk fibroin solution 3 wt. % was provided. Magnetic nanoparticles (MNP) were dispersed in silk fibroin solution by ultrasonication for several hours. The dispersion of magnetite in silk fibroin solution was cast onto glass dishes followed by solvent evaporation for 48 h. The as obtained biocomposite films were also subjected to drying under vacuum for 24 h. SF-magnetite films were obtained with 0.2, 0.3 and 0.45% magnetite content.

FTIR-ATR characterization

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra were recorded on a Bruker VERTEX 70 spectrometer in 4000 – 600 cm⁻¹ region. The samples were analyzed by attenuated transmission reflectance (ATR).

X-ray diffraction (XRD) spectra were registered on a Panalytical X'PERT MPD X-ray Diffractometer, in the range $2\theta = 10\text{--}80$. An X-ray beam characteristic to Cu K α radiation was used ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$).

Morphological information including internal structure was obtained through the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis of the gold-coated composites. The analysis has been performed using a QUANTA INSPECT F SEM device equipped with a field emission gun (FEG) with a resolution of 1.2 nm and with an X-ray energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS).

Geometrical evaluation (size and shape), crystalline structure of magnetic nanoparticles and the morphology of the BC and BC/magnetite nanocomposite were investigated by high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM) using a TECNAI F30 G² S-TWIN microscope operated at 300 kV with Energy Dispersive X-ray Analysis (EDAX) facility. Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) for crystalline structure evaluation was also performed.

Biological assay

Cell culture model:

Human adipose derived stem cells (hASCs) were isolated from subcutaneous adipose tissue during elective liposuction procedures as previously described [*Modulation of Adipogenic Conditions for Prospective Use of hADSCs in Adipose Tissue Engineering; Bianca Galateanu, Sorina Dinescu, Anisoara Cimpean, Anca Dinischiotu and Marieta Costache; Int. J. Mol. Sci. 2012, 13, 15881-15900; doi:10.3390/ijms131215881*]. All the patients involved in the study offered their written informed consent. None of them had diabetes, severe systemic illness, or was taking medication known to affect adipose tissue metabolism. All the medical procedures were performed in compliance with the Helsinki Declaration, with the approval of the Emergency Hospital for Plastic Surgery and Burns Ethical Committee (reference No. 3076/10.06.2010).

Biocompatibility assessment:

hASCs were seeded at an initial density of 1.5×10^4 cells/cm² on the composites surfaces and maintained in standard conditions of culture for one week. The viability of hASCs in contact with the novel composite materials were assessed at 48h post seeding using qualitative Live/Dead Assay and a quantitative MTT test. The cytotoxic potential of the biomaterials on hASCs was evaluated by spectrophotometric quantification of the LDH activity in culture medium at 48h post seeding.

Live/Dead Fluorescence Microscopy Assay

Cell viability on the novel composites materials was evaluated by fluorescence microscopy using Live/Dead Kit (Invitrogen, Life Technologies, Foster City, CA, USA). This method allows the simultaneous detection of both live and dead cells using calcein AM (a non-fluorescent and permeable reagent, which is converted by the intracellular esterases to the intensely green fluorescent calcein - ex/em: ~495 nm/~515 nm) and ethidium bromide dyes. Ethidium bromide enters the cells with damaged membrane, producing a bright red fluorescence when binding to nucleic acids (ex/em: ~495 nm/~635 nm). Briefly, at 48h post seeding, the hADSCs-composite bioconstructs were incubated with a staining solution prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions for 15 min at room temperature and dark. Next, the stained samples were analysed by fluorescence microscopy using an Olympus IX71 inverted microscope, and images were captured with Cell F Imaging Software (Olympus: Hamburg, Germany, 2008).

MTT Spectrophotometric Test

The viability of hASCs in contact with the composites materials were quantitatively assessed by MTT assay at 48h post seeding, in order to validate the findings revealed by Live/Dead assay. This test is based on the reduction of a tetrazolium salt solution (MTT) to purple formazan by metabolically active cells. All samples were incubated for 4 h in 1 mg/mL MTT solution (Sigma Aldrich Co.,

Steinheim, Germany) at 37⁰C. The concentration of the formazan produced by the metabolically active cells was spectrophotometrically quantified at 550 nm (Appliskan Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), after solubilization in isopropanol. The result was a sensitive assay with a colorimetric signal proportional to the viable cell number.

LDH Spectrophotometric Assay

The cytotoxic potential the novel composite materials on hASCs was evaluated using “*In vitro* toxicology assay kit lactate dehydrogenase based” (Sigma Aldrich Co., Steinheim, Germany), considering the spectrophotometric detection of lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), which is released in the culture medium by the cells with damaged membranes. As LDH is a cytosolic enzyme, its detection in the culture media is correlated with membrane damage and the potential cytotoxicity of the cellular environment. The culture media were harvested at 48h post seeding and mixed with the solutions provided in the kit, following instructions. After 20 min of incubation, the reactions was stopped with 1N hydrochloric acid (HCl) and the LDH enzymatic activity was determined by measuring the optic density of the resulting solutions at 490 nm (Appliskan Thermo Scientific).

Statistical Analysis

The statistical evaluation of the data was done using the one-way ANOVA method followed by Bonferroni’s multiple comparison test. All experiments were performed in triplicate, and the results were expressed as a mean \pm standard deviation (SD) using GraphPad Prism Software (version 3.03; GraphPad Software Inc., San Diego, CA, USA, 2002) for Windows. Differences between samples were considered statistically significant for $p < 0.05$ and highly significant for $p < 0.001$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

FTIR-ATR analysis

The results of the FTIR-ATR spectra gave us the specific absorbance wavelengths of the specific bonds which appeared in the silk fibroin/magnetite materials, confirming the structure of the new materials (fig. 1). Typical peaks of silk fibroin are 1625, 1513 and 1238 cm⁻¹, characteristic for amide I (C=O stretching), amide II (NH deformation and C–N stretching) and amide III (C–N stretching and N–H deformation). The FTIR analysis of the silk fibroin/magnetite films confirmed the spectral modification. As expected, the presence of magnetite is associated with a shifting towards left of the signals from 1625 to 1650 cm⁻¹, 1513 to 1535 cm⁻¹. The characteristic peak for OH and NH groups becomes broader with the presence of the magnetite in the material.

This shifting of the amides is characteristic for β -sheet structure of silk fibroin within the composite films.

Fig.1. FTIR-ATR spectra of SF and SF-MAG biocomposites

XRD analysis

XRD-diffraction was also employed to check the presence of magnetite in the silk fibroin matrix and to investigate the crystalline structure of the biocomposites (fig. 2).

Fig.2. XRD diffractograms of magnetite, SF and SF-MAG biocomposites

The XRD pattern of the pure magnetite presents the peaks at $2\theta=30.27^\circ$, 35.7° , 43.44° și 57.14° , which are indexed to (220), (311), (400) and (511) for Fe_3O_4 (magnetite with face-centered cubic system). Diffractograms of SF-MAG biocomposites reveal similar maxima to magnetite, especially at 35.7° ((311) index for magnetite) slightly shifted according to nanocomposite composition. Pure SF protein has a specific maxima at around 20° .

SEM morphological investigation

Micro- and nanostructural characteristics of SF-MAG composites were revealed by SEM analysis. Figure 3 shows the nanostructure of the magnetite and the surface of crude SF film. Fig.4. reveal the structure of SF-MAG 0.45 % biocomposites at two different magnifications. The presence of magnetite onto the surface or within the silk fibroin can be noticed.

Fig.3. SEM microphotographs of pure magnetite nanoparticles (left) and crude SF film surface (right)

Fig.4. SEM microphotographs of SF-MAG 0.45% biocomposite at 2000x and 40000x

Biological assay

LIVE/DEAD fluorescent microscopy assay

In order to examine hASCs survival on the tested biomaterials, cellular the viability was evaluated at 48 hours post-seeding by fluorescence microscopy (Fig. 5), based on the simultaneous staining of live (green labelled) and dead (red labelled) cells.

After 48 h post-seeding bright green-labeled cells were observed on the surface of A0 (crude SF film), A1, A2 and A3 biocomposites (SF-MAG 0.2, 0.3 and 0.45 %), as a proof of their survival. As shown in fig. 5, bright green living hASCs on the surface of all biomaterials display their characteristic spindle-like morphology.

Fig.5. Fluorescence microscopy micrographs revealing live and dead cells on FN (A0), SF-MAG 0.2 % (A1), SF-MAG 0.3 % (A2), SF-MAG 0.45 % (A3) at 48 hours post-seeding

Additionally, the highest cell density was observed on silk fibroin A0 film, while the amount of green living cells on A1, A2 and A3 was found approximately equal, but lower than A0.

Quantification of the cellular viability and proliferation status

hASCs viability A0, A1, A2 and A3 was quantitatively determined by MTT spectrophotometric assay. The spectrophotometric data obtained were graphically represented in fig. 6. Our data revealed that after 48h of culture hASCs survived in direct contact with the tested biomaterials. No significant differences were detected, neither between the samples and the fibroin film, nor the three compositions of fibroin and magnetite.

Fig.6. Quantification of hASCs viability on A0, A1, A2 and A3 surfaces, as revealed by MTT test at 48 hours post-seeding

These results suggest that all the tested magnetic biocomposites display a good biocompatibility *in vitro* on hASCs.

CONCLUSIONS

Biocomposites based on silk fibroin and magnetic nanoparticles were developed in this study by dispersion of magnetite in silk fibroin matrix followed by solvent casting. Physico-chemical and morphological characterization was employed for magnetic silk fibroin biomaterials. The biological assessment show good biocompatibility of the composite films on human adipose derived stem cells (hASCs). These biocomposite materials will be further tested for wound healing applications as they show promising results in this field of tissue engineering applications.

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